

THE LEADER AND HIS QUALITIES IN THE VIEW OF FOREIGN SCIENTISTS AND RESEARCHERS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the leader and his qualities based on the opinions of foreign scientists and researchers. In addition, as a result of the studies conducted on the topic, the views of foreign researchers served to enrich the content of the article.*

Keywords: *leader, social management, professional manager, leadership qualities, professional competence, leader, management.*

INTRODUCTION.

The demand for specialists in the field of social management is increasing day by day in every aspect of our life, which is becoming more and more synchronized with today's globalization process. Because their tasks include not only the timely identification of acute social conflicts, but also their professional, interested and effective resolution. The management culture of the leader serves as a factor for the optimization and further development of social relations, ensuring the advanced and progressive development of each country, and the implementation of vital tasks.

From the point of view of the subject of management, management culture means qualities such as "a high level of formation of intellectual, emotional-volitional, moral, physical qualities, efficiency and stability", as well as their sum allows to solve professional problems in the field of social management at a high level will give.

Currently, great attention is paid to the formation of new professional managers who have leadership qualities that allow them to perceive and satisfy the specific needs of the group at each stage of activity.

The leadership and leadership qualities of a school principal, a theater director, and the head of a business structure are different. In addition, there is no doubt that their list may be different for leaders of different management levels, for example, the head of the school and the deputy for scientific and methodical work. This determines the need to study leadership and leadership qualities in relation to the specific conditions of the leader's professional activity.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.

The development of intellectual and moral leadership and leadership qualities of a person is of great importance in the management culture of the leader. Such qualities include professional competence, decency (honesty, adherence to generally accepted moral standards), without which it is difficult or impossible to have power, that is, management.

Developed intelligence is manifested in the speed of understanding the essence of the problem, the flexibility of the mind, foresight, the ability to plan and set goals. Social competence of the leader and his benevolence in his relations with team members, communication culture, clear and fluent expression of his thoughts, correct listening to employees, giving comments, giving advice, attentiveness, respect for the dignity of other people ability to provide skills, ability to understand them, get to know their concerns and problems, quickly and accurately assess the situation, know and take into account the characteristics, interests, requests and expectations of all

members of the team. helps to be Therefore, it is more important for leadership to correctly assess the situation, its own strengths and the capabilities of the team.

It is also worth noting that the effective work of the head of each educational organization is one of the main elements of the success of this educational organization. The leader plays a decisive role in improving the effectiveness of education and implementing national reforms in the field of education. Today, it works in a dynamically changing educational environment determined by external and internal factors.

The topic of leadership plays an important role in the dynamics of group and community processes, it has its own historical character and reflects the existing socio-economic relations in society. In its general sense, leadership is the ability of a person to influence others, thereby motivating them to achieve their goals in ways that are necessary for a leader.

The relevance of the topic of leadership in leadership activity is that many Russian, Belarusian and foreign scientists and researchers have dealt with issues of leadership qualities and are still dealing with them today. However, the analysis of pedagogical, sociological, philosophical and psychological literature on the problem shows that, despite so many researches, there is still no clear opinion about this phenomenon and its components.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

In the theory of leadership qualities of F. Woods, it was emphasized that the leader is given a unique talent that distinguishes him from his followers, and that the qualities defining the leader can be systematized. A similar opinion was expressed by M. Weber, who emphasized that the main thing for an effective leader is the presence of charisma, which reveals the main qualities necessary for a leader in managing a team.

R. Ketell has a different point of view, and says that the personality of the leader is primarily influenced by heredity and environment, in other words, some qualities necessary for a leader (for example, curiosity) are formed at an early age. emphasizes. He admits that the rest of his qualities (for example, ambition, politeness) will be formed in the following years. In general, the set of qualities that apply to a leader varies depending on the sphere of society's life, and with the complexity of the tasks facing the leader, the range of skills he should have expands, it is no exaggeration to say.

Unlike F. Woods, M. Weber and R. Katell, some researchers emphasize that there are no specific qualities of a leader, that there are situations that force a person to show himself as a leader. For example, in 1928, G. Person puts forward the hypothesis that every situation determines the qualities of a leader that should act effectively in new conditions, and the characteristics of a person who can be defined as a leader in a particular case are the product itself. J. Hemphill also joined this point of view.

In addition to these opinions, other scientists also expressed their opinions about the leader and his qualities. Among them, it was considered appropriate to highlight the opinions of B. Nanus and P. Drucker, a well-known researcher in the field of leadership. And below are their views:

Scientist B. Nanus believed that a leader has seven main abilities:

- 1) understanding;
- 2) the art of making changes;
- 3) the ability to build organizations;
- 4) advanced learning ability;
- 5) initiative;

- 6) the ability to understand interdependence;
- 7) high integrity and integrity of character.

P. Drucker, a well-known American researcher in the field of leadership, refers to the main leadership skills as follows:

- * the ability to value one's time;
- * ability to make decisions;
- * ability to form and develop effective working groups;
- * ability to focus on results.

The analysis carried out on this issue shows that there are significant differences in the positions of individual authors regarding the list of the main abilities and skills of the leader and their main characteristics. Of course, these headlights can be due to personal experiences. Or because the views do not correspond to each other.

Above, when we refer to the views of the world's famous scientists and researchers about the leader and his characteristic qualities and analyze them one by one, it is not difficult to understand that the identification of the types of leaders and their description still does not fully and clearly answer what makes a person a leader. therefore, it is necessary to raise the issue of skills, abilities or abilities that help a person become a leader. For example, O. Teed distinguishes 11 leadership skills and qualities as follows:

1. self-management ability;
2. reasonable personal values;
3. clear personal goals;
4. problem solving skills;
5. ability to innovate;
6. the ability to influence others;
7. knowledge of management approaches;
8. leadership ability;
9. ability to train and develop subordinates;
10. focus on personal growth;
11. ability to form effective working groups.

In the 1989s of the 20th century, Leigh Cringer proposed to consider the leader not in terms of his qualities, situations, abilities, but in terms of his actions. That is, at the first stage, an effective leader evaluates others, adapts and shapes the tasks to be performed. In the second stage, he must harmonize his ideas, of course, with his followers, using all necessary means. The third stage is the development of trust. In the fourth stage, the leader himself serves as an example and a motivator for the behavior of others.

Upon closer analysis, one can realize that these views of Leigh Cringer are not inappropriate. Because the leader is constantly active, his actions serve to ensure the future.

As a result of conducting research about the leader and his qualities, he got acquainted with the views, theories and opinions of many scientists. J. Howell also takes a worthy place among these learned sciences and researchers.

In J. Howell's research, information can be found on the effective leader's: use of power for the benefit of others; connects goals with followers' needs and visions; learns based on criticism in his appeal; encourages followers to think independently and question the validity of their own opinions; supporter of open two-way communication; educates and supports followers, shares

recognition with others; relies on internal motives to determine moral actions; the most important thing is that it is an example for the collective.

CONCLUSION.

Comparing the lists of leader actions identified by different authors, it is easy to see that each researcher has their own unique view of what a leader should do and behave. This means that it is impossible to single out and characterize the general actions, abilities or skills of a leader, which allows other scientists to further reveal the issue of leadership, to find new truths for research.

Regarding the question of the qualities that a leader should have and their description, it should be noted that universal leadership qualities have not yet been determined, so researchers in the field of leadership and leadership qualities sometimes have completely different opinions. From their point of view, the various qualities listed above are leadership, and moreover, some research on such qualities is conflicting.

Thus, by analyzing the theoretical aspects of this issue, we can conclude that a leader is a person who stands out from a group of people due to the presence of certain personal qualities and skills and occupies this position, and in addition, his actions are a prototype of a leader, the death of such a person there is a specific leadership style, which often depends on the type of organization, the task to be solved and the followers themselves. Also, leadership qualities themselves are determined by genetic factors, upbringing and educational conditions, and social environment and situational aspects.

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